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Mini Review

Mastocytosis: Principles and Pitfalls in the Diagnosis of a Unique Disease

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Abstract

Mastocytosis, a hematological neoplasm, manifests with diverse clinical, molecular, and histomorphological features. This review explores the different subtypes of mastocytosis, focusing on the role of molecular pathology and histomorphology in diagnosing systemic mastocytosis (SM). Systemic mastocytosis is characterized by histologically confirmed extracutaneous involvement, presenting a diagnostic challenge due to its rarity and diverse subtypes, ranging from occult SM to mast cell leukemia. The complexity of accurate SM diagnosis underscores the necessity for a comprehensive understanding of the disease spectrum. Mastocytosis emerges as a rare, multifaceted disease, predominantly affecting children in the cutaneous form and adults in the systemic variant. The review advocates a multidisciplinary diagnostic approach involving experienced hematopathologists and haematoooncologists, employing conventional histomorphology, immunohistochemistry, and molecular techniques. This holistic approach is crucial for accurate diagnosis, especially in light of recent therapeutic advances, particularly the growing importance of tyrosine kinase inhibitors (TKI) in the management of mastocytosis.

Introduction

Mastocytosis comprises a diverse group of disorders caused by the clonal proliferation of abnormal mast cells, leading to their accumulation in the skin and/or various extracutaneous organs. As a recognition of its distinct biology, mastocytosis was removed from the subtypes of Myeloproliferative Neoplasms (MPN) and is listed as a separate entity in the 5th Edition of the WHO classification [1] and in the International Consensus Classification 2022 [2]. Mastocytosis exhibits a wide range of clinical and histomorphological features and it is essential to distinguish between the pure cutaneous and systemic variants of mastocytosis [3-5]. Cutaneous Mastocytosis (CM) is limited to the skin, occurs most commonly in children, and generally has a good prognosis [6,7]. On the other hand, Systemic Mastocytosis (SM) is the most common form of mastocytosis diagnosed in adults and is defined by mast cell infiltration of one or more extracutaneous organs (with or without skin involvement) with a variable prognosis. SM is classified into non-advanced variants (bone marrow mastocytosis or BMM, indolent systemic mastocytosis or ISM, and smoldering systemic mastocytosis or SSM) and advanced variants (aggressive systemic mastocytosis or ASM, systemic mastocytosis with associated haematological neoplasm or SM-AHN, and mast cell leukaemia or MCL). Treatment approaches may focus on managing symptoms or eliminating neoplastic

mast cells, with multikinase inhibitors targeting KIT D816V and other key signalling molecules emerging as new options for advanced SM.

Due to the rarity of the disease and the heterogeneity of SM, which often presents with non-specific and overlapping features (ranging from occult SM to mast cell leukemia), establishing a definitive and accurate diagnosis can be very challenging. Comprehensive care for patients with mastocytosis requires a multidisciplinary team approach, and referral to centers with expertise in mastocytosis is strongly recommended.

Classification

Table 1.

Table 1: Classification of mastocytosis.	
Cutaneous Mastocytosis	
Urticaria pigmentosa/Maculopapular Cutaneous Mastocytosis	
Diffuse Cutaneous Mastocytosis	
Cutaneous mastocytoma	
Systemic Mastocytosis	
Bone Marrow Mastocytosis	
Indolent Systemic Mastocytosis	
Smouldering Systemic Mastocytosis	
Aggressive Systemic Mastocytosis	
SM with an Associated Haematologic Neoplasm	
Mast Cell Leukaemia	
Mast Cell Sarcoma	

Diagnostic approach

Using the updated WHO and ICC criteria of 2022 is essential for diagnosing mastocytosis (Table 2).

The histopathological hallmark is a compact infiltrate consisting of a cohesive cluster of at least 15 mast cells (the only major diagnostic criterion).

Additionally, four minor criteria have been defined:

1. Activating point mutations in *KIT* (in particular p.D816V)
2. Marked increase in spindle-shaped mast cells (at least 25% of the whole mast cell population)
3. Aberrant expression of CD25 (IL2-receptor alpha) and/or CD30 (CD2 is of minor relevance here) by mast cells
4. Significant increase of serum tryptase (> 20 ng/ul)

Diagnosis of SM is established when the major criterion and at least 1 minor criterion or at least 3 minor criteria are present.

Histomorphology

In over 90% of patients, the diagnosis of Systemic Mastocytosis (SM) relies on histomorphological analysis of bone marrow, pure cytological methods can only be applied in mast cell leukemia [8]. Basic dyes like Giemsa and Toluidine Blue, along with immunohistochemical stains, are used in this process [9]. Basic dyes reveal the presence of metachromatic intracytoplasmic granules, which are unique to mast cells and contain a wide range of bioactive mediators. No other human cell contains such metachromatic granules (Figure 1). The metachromatic granules of basophilic granulocytes are water soluble and therefore not detectable in routinely processed tissue using formalin as a fixative and are therefore of no diagnostic relevance in hematopathology.

As atypical mast cells are often hypogranular (or even agranular), it is essential to always use an appropriate antibody panel to confirm or exclude the diagnosis of SM:

1. Anti-tryptase
2. Anti-CD117 (KIT)
3. Anti-CD25
4. Anti-CD30

The mature immunophenotype of mast cells is defined by the coexpression of tryptase and CD117, a feature consistently present in both normal and reactive (hyperplastic) states [10]. On the other hand, the expression of aberrant antigens such as CD25 (and, to a lesser extent, CD30) is almost exclusively observed in clonally mutated mast cells within the setting of SM [11,12] (Figure 1). The only exception to this rule is the occurrence of CD25-expressing (atypical) mast cells in rare cases of myeloid/lymphoid neoplasms with eosinophilia carrying a *PDGFR-alpha* fusion gene [13]. It's important to note that a cell lacking CD117 expression cannot be classified as a mast cell.

Primary diagnosis of SM in extramedullary tissues is rare, occurring in <10% of patients. Here, the GI tract mucosa plays a major role [14-16]. It is important to know that in at least 50% of cases of SM involving the GI tract mucosa (Figure 1), tryptase expression appears to be reduced or even absent, leading to an incomplete aberrant immunophenotype, especially when aberrant expression of CD25 (and/or CD30) is seen. It is therefore highly recommended to use anti-CD117 for initial screening of mast cell numbers in the GI tract mucosa. A primary diagnosis of SM in lymph nodes, liver, or spleen is possible but seems to be a very rare event [17,18]. Diagnostic criteria for SM should be applied to extramedullary tissues, but precise definitions have not yet been published.

Histopathological findings in SM, with special emphasis on the bone marrow

It is crucial to delineate the type of infiltration pattern in order to subtype SM. Conventional stainings such as Giemsa allow a rough orientation but adequate immunohistochemical stainings are a prerequisite for a correct diagnosis in all patients.

Table 2: Diagnostic criteria of systemic mastocytosis according to the WHO HAEM5 and ICC 2022.

The diagnosis is SM if at least 1 major and 1 minor criterion or 3 minor criteria are fulfilled.
Major criterion
Multifocal dense infiltrates of mast cells (≥ 15 mast cells in aggregates) detected in sections of bone marrow and/or other extracutaneous organ(s).
Minor criteria
a. > 25% of all mast cells are atypical cells (type I or type II) on bone marrow smears or are spindle-shaped in dense and diffuse mast cell infiltrates in sections of BM or other extracutaneous organ(s).
b. Activating <i>KIT</i> point mutation(s) at codon 816 or in other critical regions of <i>KIT</i> in bone marrow or another extracutaneous organ(s). [§]
c. Mast cells in bone marrow, blood, or another extracutaneous organ(s) aberrantly express one or more of the following antigens: CD2, CD25, CD30*
d. Baseline serum tryptase concentration > 20 ng/mL in the absence of a myeloid AHN. In the case of a known HaT, the tryptase level could be adjusted.**
Mast Cell Sarcoma
[§] In the absence of a <i>KIT</i> mutation particularly in cases with eosinophilia, the ICC recommends excluding the presence of tyrosine kinase gene fusions associated with M/LN-Eo
*CD30, which is aberrantly expressed in a significant proportion of SM cases, has been added as an additional immunophenotypic finding (in the updated WHO classification HAEM5 and in the ICC of myeloid neoplasms)
**Both the WHO HAEM5 and the ICC stress that elevated tryptase levels in SM-AHN (or SM-AMN) do not count as minor criteria.

Figure 1: Basic features of SM (A-C; bone marrow infiltrate and D-F; infiltrate of the colon).

A) Systemic mastocytosis (undifferentiated subtype). (Giemsa stain): Compact infiltrate consisting of >15 mast cells exhibiting both spindle shape and moderate hypogranulation. B) Systemic mastocytosis (well-differentiated subtype) (Giemsa stain): Compact infiltrate consisting of >15 mast cells showing both exclusive roundness of the cytoplasm and signs of hypergranulation. C) Anti-CD25 immunohistochemistry: Compact mast cell infiltrates in systemic mastocytosis involving the bone marrow. Strong aberrant expression of CD25 by atypical mast cells. Note the specific annular, membrane-associated immunostaining. D-F) Systemic (intestinal) mastocytosis mimicking eosinophilic colitis with mast cells exhibiting an incomplete-aberrant immunophenotype. D) H&E stain: Lamina propria mucosae is filled with densely packed mature eosinophilic granulocytes leading to an initial diagnosis of "eosinophilic colitis". E) Anti-CD117 immunohistochemistry: Immunostaining reveals CD117-expressing mast cells forming compact band-like infiltrates in a subepithelial position. F) Anti-tryptase immunohistochemistry: The number of tryptase-expressing mast cells is low obviously reflecting those mast that do not belong to the neoplastic clone. Scale bar A-C 5µm; D-F 50 µm.

The following main types of infiltration do occur:

1. Diffuse-interstitial without significantly increased mast cell numbers and compact infiltrates;
2. Diffuse-interstitial with increased mast cell numbers but without compact infiltrates;
3. Multifocal with disseminated compact infiltrates but without significant diffuse-interstitial infiltration;
4. Multifocal with disseminated compact infiltrates and with significant diffuse-interstitial infiltration and
5. Packed

The diffuse-interstitial infiltration consists of loosely scattered mast cells, sometimes forming small groups, but compact infiltrates are absent. In typical cases of SM, there is a high proportion of spindle-shaped mast cells, sometimes arranged in a meshwork. SM cases presenting with infiltration patterns 1 and 2 are easily overlooked and may cause problems for the diagnosing pathologist. Multifocal infiltration patterns 3 and 4 are the most common and easy to recognize. The compact infiltrates often contain not only mast cells but also a mixture of lymphocytes and eosinophils in varying numbers. Reticulin fibres are always increased and collagen fibrosis may occur. The degree of fibrosis may vary

within a patient's compact infiltrates. Packed is defined by diffuse infiltration with almost complete destruction of the pre-existing microarchitecture.

While the majority of SM patients with diffuse interstitial and multifocal infiltration have completely intact haematopoiesis, in a minority of cases another (non-mast cell) haematological neoplasm can be detected. This is usually a myeloid, rarely a lymphoid neoplasm. Almost all defined subtypes of myeloid neoplasms can occur, with a marked preponderance of Myelodysplastic/Myeloproliferative Neoplasms (MDS/MPN), of which Chronic Myelomonocytic Leukaemia (CMML) is the most common [4].

Please refer to Figure 2 for a diagnostic workup of a patient with suspected mastocytosis.

Subtypes of SM

According to the updated classification system of mastocytosis, the following subtypes of SM can be distinguished (note that cutaneous mastocytosis is strictly limited to the skin and almost always occurs in children):

1. Bone Marrow Mastocytosis (BMM)
2. Indolent SM (ISM)
3. Smoldering SM (SSM)

Figure 1: Diagnostic workup of a patient with suspected mastocytosis.

4. Aggressive SM (ASM)
5. SM with an Associated Haemetological Neoplasm (SM-AHN)
6. Mast Cell Leukemia (MCL)

ISM is the most common subtype of SM (80% of cases) with skin and bone marrow involvement. The skin lesions are macroscopically and histopathologically indistinguishable from cutaneous mastocytosis (urticaria pigmentosa adultorum). ISM is usually associated with infiltration patterns 3 and 4, but pattern 2 may also be seen (20% - 30% of cases). BMM is much rarer than ISM, but the absence of the leading clinical symptom of skin efflorescences and the low degree of infiltration are the reasons why it is often not detected. BMM is usually associated with unexpected osteoporosis in younger and middle-aged males, but also with anaphylactic reactions due to hymenoptera stings showing a strong association with infiltration pattern 2. SSM is a rare subtype with marked multifocal bone marrow infiltration (usually 20% - 30%, or

even more), morphologically indistinguishable from ASM, but with at least one clinical B-finding according to WHO definitions.

ASM, MCL, and SM-AHN belong to the so-called group of advanced SM. Among aggressive SM SM-AHN is by far the most common subtype, but is often difficult to diagnose because both disease compartments need to be recognized and correctly defined according to WHO and ICC criteria. All infiltration patterns mentioned above can be seen in SM-AHN. In the rare event of MCL and packed marrow infiltration by atypical mast cells, normal blood cell precursors but also the AHN compartment may be overlooked. The presence of activating point mutations associated with myeloid neoplasms is crucial for the detection of SM-AHN. However, the AHN usually obscures the SM, which may be morphologically almost undetectable in some of these patients ("occult" SM). Typically, SM progresses in the "empty" marrow and thus is recognizable only after cytoreductive therapy. This is especially true for patients with initially diagnosed "KIT D816V-positive acute myeloid leukemia/AML", which often actually represents SM-AHN/AML. ASM is rare and exhibits multifocal and marked bone marrow infiltration (> 30% - 40%). ASM is a clinicopathological diagnosis because it requires the presence of at least one C-finding. C findings are defined as clinical signs of organ insufficiency due to proven mast cell infiltration. MCL is the only subtype of SM that can be diagnosed on the basis of cytomorphological findings alone. If the number of mast cells in bone marrow smears exceeds 20% of all nucleated cells, or if mast cells represent > 10% of circulating leukocytes in the blood, a diagnosis of MCL can be made at first glance. "Pure" MCL almost always shows diffuse and packed bone marrow infiltration. Leukemic and aleukemic variants of MCL occur based on the number of circulating atypical mast cells (> 10% in leukemic MCL, which is actually very rare). A fascinating disease is the coexistence of MCL and AML (Figure 3 A-E). Due to modern treatment strategies, patients with SM survive much longer than in the past, and the transformation of ISM, SSM, or ASM into a secondary malignancy is rare.

Mast cell sarcoma

Mast Cell Sarcoma (MCS) is an extremely rare subvariant of mastocytosis [20,21]. Two main variants are separated:

1. Primary MCS when cutaneous and systemic mastocytosis are excluded, and
2. Secondary MCS-like tumors developing in the progressive and often final disease phase of patients with SM.

Primary MCS has been observed in different tissue sites and apparently is usually misdiagnosed due to its sarcomatous infiltration (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Mast cell leukemia with coexisting AML (A-E), Mast cell sarcoma (G-M), and differential diagnosis myelomastocytic leukemia (F) (19) and (N-P) chronic basophilic leukemia.

A) H&E stain: Markedly hypercellular bone marrow diffusely infiltrated by medium-sized blastoid cells. Some loosely scattered megakaryocytes are also shown. Dilated sinuses. B) Anti-tryptase immunohistochemistry: Immunostaining reveals abundant tryptase-positive cells. C) Anti-CD30 immunohistochemistry: Many tumor cells including multinucleated large cells co-express CD30. D - E) Papanicolaou (Papanheim) stain: Bone marrow smear reveals marked hypercellularity. Higher magnification (E) shows atypical mast cells with vacuolated cytoplasm and metachromatic granules including multinucleated forms accounting for more than 20% of nucleated cells. F: Myelomastocytic leukemia (Papanicolaou stain) The bone marrow smear shows an abundance of blast cells with large pale nuclei and few intracytoplasmic metachromatic granules (= metachromatic blast cells). G-M; Mast cell sarcoma: G (Giemsa stain) Tissue from a large intraabdominal mass lesion with clinical suspicion of malignant lymphoma. Conventional staining at first glance is consistent with such a diagnosis, however, only CD117 (H; I) was expressed by tumor cells, and all lymphocytic markers were negative. Additional immunohistochemistry with anti-tryptase (K, L) finally revealed the mast cell nature of the tumor. M) Anti-CD30 immunohistochemistry: A significant proportion of the tumour cells expressed CD30, which could easily have led to a false diagnosis of lymphoma. N-P; Chronic basophilic leukemia in blast crisis (CBL-BC) (N); H&E staining: Bone marrow is extremely hypercellular with focal infiltrates of blastoid cells, strongly expressing CD61 (O). In other parts of the bone marrow, mature granulocytes expressing tryptase are detected (P).

Scale bar A-D and G-P 50µm; E-F 5µm.

Mast cell activation syndrome

To prove or exclude infiltration of SM in the GI tract mucosa poses a common challenge in patients with Mast Cell Activation Syndrome (MCAS). MCAS, being exceptionally rare, is not diagnosed based on morphology. The main clinical feature is a transient increase of mast cell-mediated mediators in the blood during an allergic or even anaphylactic event, but these increases are of very limited duration [22]. 90% of mucosal biopsies from the GI tract do not display any signs of SM, both morphologically and molecularly, as *KIT* p.D816V is typically absent. The count of intramucosal mast cells exhibits significant variability both within individuals and across different individuals. The only proof of SM involving the GI tract mucosa is the presence of compact often band-like, sometimes micronodular mast cell infiltrates in the lamina propria mucosae. In rare instances, mast cells can completely fill the connective tissue of the mucosal layer. Moreover, in at least 50% of patients mast cells exhibit an incomplete-aberrant immunophenotype, lacking tryptase expression (Figure 3). Therefore, anti-tryptase antibodies are not suitable for screening mast numbers in SM patients. The detection of *KIT* p.D816V completes the diagnosis of SM in the GI tract.

Molecular findings

As mentioned in the beginning, the diagnosis of systemic mastocytosis is based on a combination of clinical, histopathological, and molecular criteria. A minor criterion is the demonstration of clonality by the detection of activating mutations of the *KIT* gene. The *KIT* p.D816V mutation (located in the Tyrosine Kinase (TK) domain) is found in the majority (90%) of cases of systemic mastocytosis and is considered a hallmark of the disease.

The frequency of *KIT* mutation in systemic mastocytosis varies according to the subtype. In Indolent Systemic Mastocytosis (ISM), the mutation is detected in more than 90% of cases. In aggressive forms, such as Aggressive Systemic Mastocytosis (ASM) and Mast Cell Leukaemia (MCL), and in WDSM, the mutation is less common [23-25]. In these subtypes, other *KIT* mutations outside the TK domain may be detected.

In SM-AHN, the *KIT* mutation may be present not only in the mast cells but also in the haematopoietic compartment, suggesting a common progenitor [26]. Usually, SM with multilineage *KIT* mutation (and high Variant Allele Frequency (VAF)) has an aggressive course, especially if other secondary mutations such as *ASXL1*, *SRSF2*, or *RUNX1* are present [27-29]. Particularly in ISM with low VAF, it is important to use sensitive methods such as digital-droplet-PCR [30] or suppression-PCR [31] for the detection of *KIT* mutations to avoid false negative results [32].

Differential diagnosis

In instances of Indolent Systemic Mastocytosis (ISM), there may be disseminated follicle-like lymphocytic aggregates in close proximity to or intermingled with the neoplastic mast cells. This pattern can give the appearance of a low-grade malignant non-Hodgkin's lymphoma. At first glance, lymphocytic lymphomas such as Chronic Lymphocytic Leukemia (CLL) and Lymphoplasmacytic Lymphoma (LPL) can be easily misdiagnosed due to their high mast cell content [33]. The presence of an immature immunophenotype in mast cells, characterized by the co-expression of CD25 and/or CD30, helps to confirm the diagnosis of ISM. On the other hand, an aberrant immunophenotype in the lymphoid compartment, featuring the co-expression of CD20, CD23, and CD5, aids in establishing the diagnosis of CLL. To further support these diagnoses, additional molecular studies can be performed to demonstrate the clonality of mast cells (via *KIT* p.D816V) or lymphoid cells (through IgH rearrangement or *MYD88* p.L265P mutation in LPL).

In a significant number of cases of high-grade systemic mastocytosis (including aggressive systemic mastocytosis, systemic mastocytosis with associated hematological neoplasm, and mast cell leukemia), a majority of neoplastic mast cells express high levels of CD30. Without anti-tryptase staining, there's a risk of misinterpreting compact mast cell infiltrates as a malignant lymphoma (such as Hodgkin's sarcoma or anaplastic large cell lymphoma) or even a malignant germ cell tumor [34].

Differentiating Systemic Mastocytosis with Associated Hematological Neoplasm and eosinophilia (SM-AHN) from Myeloid/Lymphoid Neoplasms with eosinophilia (MLN-TK) is a challenging task [13]. This difficulty arises because atypical mast cell infiltrates with the expression of CD25 may be prominent in myeloid/lymphoid neoplasms carrying a *PDGFR-alpha* fusion gene. Additional molecular analysis is essential; detection of either the *PDGFR-alpha* fusion gene (MLN-TK) or the *KIT* p.D816V mutation (SM-AHN) is critical for correct diagnosis.

The main differential diagnosis of MCL is myelomastocytic leukemia [35] (MML, Figure 2). MML represents an advanced myeloid neoplasm characterized by an increased presence of blasts, as well as a significant rise in immature mast cells and/or metachromatic blast cells (comprising more than 10% of nucleated cells in bone marrow smears). Mast cells in MML typically express CD117 and tryptase but lack CD2 and CD25. While the *KIT* mutant p. D816V is not detectable, other *KIT* mutations are sporadically identified. In contrast to the spindle-shaped mast cells and compact focal infiltrates commonly found in Systemic Mastocytosis (SM), mast cells in MML are neither spindle-shaped nor do they

form compact focal infiltrates, presenting a clear contrast. Immunohistochemical markers recommended for suspected MML include CD34, CD117, tryptase, and CD25.

Additionally, distinguishing basophilic leukemia from MCL can pose a challenge due to the abundance of round tryptase-expressing neoplastic cells in both conditions (Figure 3). However, a key differentiation lies in the expression of CD117 (KIT) – a marker present on mast cells of MCL but absent on neoplastic basophils in basophilic leukemia.

Conclusion

Mastocytosis is a rare multifaceted disease with a broad clinical and histomorphological spectrum including various subtypes, in particular (pure) cutaneous (almost always children) and systemic variants (usually adults). Therefore, a multidisciplinary approach with experienced hematopathologists and haemato-oncologists using conventional histomorphology, immunohistochemistry, and molecular techniques is required for correct diagnosis. A correct diagnosis is crucial for the patient regarding recent developments in therapy with special emphasis on Tyrosine Kinase Inhibitors (TKI).

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